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[Patient groups and generic companies criticize two US patent bills](#) : The Senate Judiciary Committee is marking up two bipartisan patent reform bills that critics say would raise prices and delay generic market entry. The first bill would change the Patent Trial and Appeal Board review process, potentially limiting the ability of generic drug makers to challenge patents early. The second bill would expand patent eligibility, raising concerns about pharmaceutical companies using patent "thickets" to extend monopolies and delay more affordable drugs. Once marked up, the committee will send the bills to the full Senate

[FTC sues drug middlemen for inflating insulin prices](#): The FTC filed lawsuits against the three largest pharmacy benefit managers (PBMs) for manipulating markets to increase the price of insulin for patients. This follows a July 2024 report by the FTC that alleged that PBMs have led to vertical integration and concentration in the prescription drug market, causing higher prices and lower accessibility across the United States. In the news release, the FTC stated that it could act against drug manufacturers that engage in this conduct.

[Draghi report touts path to pull EU pharma from 'slow agony'](#): As part of former Italian Prime Minister Mario Draghi's competitiveness report on the EU's economic health and competitiveness, he emphasized that the EU's pharma sector faces "slow agony" due to complex regulations, high costs, and lack of investment. The report suggests key reforms to revitalize the industry, including reducing regulatory hurdles, improving access to funding, and fostering innovation, without which, the report claims, Europe's competitiveness and market share in the global pharmaceutical market will continue to decline.

[Innovative pharma-government partnership to enhance UK clinical trials](#): The UK government announced a £400 million public-private partnership, the Voluntary Scheme for Branded Medicine Pricing, Access and Growth (VPAG), to boost the country's life sciences sector. A majority (75%) of the funding will be dedicated to increasing the capacity of commercial clinical trials through the establishment 18 new research centres, while an additional 20% of the funding will be directed towards environmentally friendly pharmaceutical manufacturing. The remaining funding will be dedicated to improving patient access to innovative treatments and medicines.

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Study combines data and molecular simulations to accelerate drug discovery:

Researchers from the University of Cincinnati College of Medicine and Cincinnati Children's Hospital have found a way to combine the database from the Library of Integrated Network-based Cellular Signatures (LINCS) to screen small molecules with potential therapeutic effects with targeted docking simulations to model those molecules' interactions with target proteins. The process has reduced the amount of time needed to screen potential compounds from months to hours and has the potential to significantly expedite the drug discovery process.